
DEEP WITHOUT GRADIENTS: A FORENSIC ANALYSIS OF LOCAL PLASTICITY

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ABSTRACT

Biologically plausible learning remains an open challenge in Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) due to the dependence of the backpropagation algorithm on gradient propagation and weight symmetric constraints. In this work, we investigate Event Gated Local Plasticity (EGLP), a local learning mechanism that incorporates Hebbian plasticity, Direct Feedback Alignment (DFA) and sparse surprise triggered update gating. In contrast to gradient based learning mechanisms, the EGLP framework performs local hidden layer updates using neuron level modulation while decoupling hidden layers from end to end gradient flow. We conduct comparative analysis against supervised, unsupervised and frozen feature based learning baselines on MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets. The experimental results demonstrate that EGLP can learn meaningful feature representation with significantly lesser number of weight updates in the hidden layer and lower computational cost ($3\times$ reduction in FLOPs with only 20% of the update events). However, EGLP underperforms backpropagation, specifically in deep architectures and complex computer vision tasks. The results highlight the challenges in hierarchical credit assignment and representation learning under strictly local plasticity constraints

Keywords Local Plasticity · Biologically Plausible Learning · Hebbian Learning · Direct Feedback Alignment · Event Gated Learning · Artificial Neural Networks

1 Introduction

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have shown remarkable success through backpropagation algorithm [1]. The backpropagation or backprop algorithm propagates gradients across multiple layers of ANN to optimize the learnable parameters in the network. However the biological plausibility of backprop has been long criticized due to symmetric feedback weights, globally propagated error signals, and tightly coordinated updates across the network. These limitations have motivated extensive research on local plasticity mechanisms such as Hebbian learning [2], three-factor rules [3] and predictive coding frameworks [4].

In this study we investigate Event Gated Local Plasticity (EGLP), a locally contained learning framework that incorporates Hebbian learning, Direct Feedback Alignment (DFA) [5], and sparse surprise triggered update gating [6, 7]. We conduct a comparative study to examine the representational, scaling, and efficiency limitations of local plasticity mechanisms against gradient based learning. The experimental results on the benchmark datasets highlight that while EGLP can learn meaningful representations with substantially reduced update frequency and computational overhead, it consistently exhibits weaker optimization capability and poorer scaling behavior than backpropagation, particularly as network depth increases.

2 Related Works

The backpropagation algorithm [8] remains a strong optimization strategy in deep neural networks across a wide range of supervised learning tasks. However, the biological plausibility of the backpropagation algorithm has been debated as it uses symmetric feedforward and feedback weights, global error propagation across layers, and tightly coordinated updates within the network. These constraints have motivated a number of researches on alternative

learning mechanisms that are capable of operating under local plasticity. One of the earliest works on local learning includes Hebbian plasticity [9]. The Hebbian rule follows the principle that neurons that fire together strengthen their mutual connections. Classical Hebbian learning rules rely on local information, typically involving presynaptic and postsynaptic correlations. Oja [10] introduced a normalized extension of the Hebbian rule where an activity based decay term constrains unbounded weight growth. Despite their biological significance and interpretability, the Hebbian and Oja based learning mechanisms have struggled to scale in deep supervised learning tasks.

To address these limitations, several research works have incorporated task level supervision and explored three-factor learning rules. Jiang et al. (2016) [11] proposed NeuroPlastic, a biologically inspired optimizer that enhances traditional gradient based learning by introducing a multi-signal plasticity modulation mechanism combining gradient, activity and memory based signals. Gerstner et al. (2018) [12] introduced NeoHebbian, a three-factor learning rule that extends classical Hebbian learning. Their approach includes an additional modulatory signal named the “third factor”, which can represent reward, novelty, or surprise. The framework uses simultaneous activation of presynaptic and postsynaptic neurons that creates a temporary “eligibility trace” that acts like a short term memory for the layers between neurons.

Another direction of research explored relaxing the strict gradient flow in backpropagation. Nøklund (2016) [13] proposed Direct Feedback Alignment, a biologically inspired alternative to backpropagation in which hidden layers receive error signals directly from the output layer through fixed random feedback connections. Furthermore, research studies such as Rao and Ballard [14] or Whittington and Bogacz [15] have explored predictive coding as an alternative framework for biologically plausible learning. Despite extensive research work on biologically plausible learning algorithms, comparatively very few studies have systematically investigated their scaling behavior, stability constraints, and representational limitations in deep ANNs.

3 Methodology

The EGLP framework investigates the impact on the learning dynamics of ANNs on locally constrained plasticity mechanisms. The framework combines three components, namely:

1. Local Hebbian updates in hidden layers
2. Task dependent modulation through DFA
3. Sparse global gating signals based on prediction error dynamics

3.1 Decoupled Architecture and Forward Dynamics

Firstly, the hidden layers are decoupled from the gradient based optimization to enforce the local learning constraints. For a given hidden layer l , with input $x^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and output $y^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, the activation function is calculated as follows:

$$y^{(l)} = ReLU(W^{(l)}x^{(l)} + b^{(l)}) \quad (1)$$

Subsequently, the activation tensor is detached from the computational graph during the forward pass. Hence, gradients from subsequent layers do not propagate into a given hidden layer. A terminal readout layer receives all the detached representations, which is optimized using the Adam optimizer [16].

3.2 Modulated Three-factor Local Plasticity

The hidden layers of the ANN are updated using a modulated extension of Ojha’s learning rule [17]. For a neuron i connected to another neuron j the update rule is defined as:

$$\Delta w_{ij} = \eta_{local} \cdot E(t) \cdot [m_j(y_j x_i - \phi_j(y_j^2 w_{ij}))] \quad (2)$$

where η_{local} denotes the local learning rate, $E(t)$ a scalar gating signal, m_j a modulatory factor derived from DFA, $y_j x_i$ is the Hebbian correlation term and ϕ_j is the Oja normalization term.

It should be noted that for experiments, we use $\phi_j = m_j$.

3.3 Direct Feedback Alignment (DFA)

As gradient backpropagation is disabled in the hidden layers of the ANN, the task dependent information is provided through DFA. The global error vector is calculated as follows:

$$e = z - \hat{z} \quad (3)$$

where z is the target label and \hat{z} is the prediction of the ANN.

Each error vector is projected directly onto each hidden layer using a non-learnable fixed matrix $B^{(l)}$ as follows:

$$m^{(l)} = B^{(l)}e \quad (4)$$

The resultant vector $m^{(l)}$ acts as neuron specific modulation signals that are used for local plasticity updates.

3.4 Surprise Based Event Gating

A global event controller regulates the plasticity events by observing the changes in cross-entropy loss. The controller tracks the mean μ_L and the standard deviation σ_L of the loss and an event is triggered when the loss of the current batch L_t exceeds the loss of the previous batch L_{t-1} .

The normalized surprise signal is defined as follows:

$$S_t = \frac{L_t - L_{t-1}}{\sigma_t + \epsilon} \quad (5)$$

The gating magnitude is calculated as follows:

$$E(t) = \min(\text{ReLU}(S_t), E_{max}) \quad (6)$$

where $E(t)$ is a scalar neuromodulator that gates both the timing (binary event) and the magnitude (continuous scale)

The controller operates with a fixed event budget during training. Additionally, a stochastic lower bound event probability $P(event) = 0.05$ is maintained until the event budget is exhausted.

3.5 Stability and Normalization Heuristics

To improve representational stability across the layers of the ANN, we incorporate two more mechanisms, namely Frozen Batch Normalization and Soft-Winner-Take-All (Soft-WTA). The Frozen Batch Normalization is used to stabilize the feature distributions during training. During an initial warm-up phase the normalization statistics are calculated and are kept fixed for the remaining training time. This approach helps maintain stable feature scaling across layers by preventing the normalization parameters from changing throughout training. The Soft-WTA mechanism is applied within the hidden layers of the ANN to mitigate feature collapse and encourage representation diversity. For a given training sample the the top- k activations are retained while the remaining activations are suppressed. This encourages sparse feature representations and reduces redundancy among neuron activations.

3.6 Datasets

3.6.1 MNIST

The MNIST (Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology) [18] is a standard benchmark dataset of 28×28 pixel images of handwritten digits (0-9). It consists of 60,000 images in the training set and 10,000 images in the test set. A few samples from MNIST dataset along with the corresponding labels are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A few samples from the MNIST dataset with corresponding labels

3.6.2 CIFAR-10

CIFAR-10 is a benchmark computer vision dataset consisting of 32×32 images across 10 classes. The dataset comprises of a total 60,000 samples with 6000 samples in each class. The pre-defined train-test split contains 50,000 images and 10,000 images respectively. A few samples from the CIFAR-10 dataset is plotted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: A few samples from the CIFAR-10 dataset with corresponding labels

3.6.3 Dataset Preprocessing

To ensure fair comparison the preprocessing pipeline is kept same for the two datasets. Firstly, the images are normalized so that each pixel ranges between $[0, 1]$. For MNIST we use a mean and variance of $\mu = 0.1307$ and $\sigma = 0.3081$ respectively, while for CIFAR-10 we use a mean and variance of $\mu = [0.4914, 0.4822, 0.4465]$ and $\sigma = [0.2023, 0.1994, 0.2010]$ respectively. This is followed by flattening the images into N dimension vector, for MNIST the 28×28 images are flattened into 784 dimensional dimension and for CIFAR-10 $3 \times 32 \times 32$ images are flattened into a 3072 dimensional vector.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Experimental Setup

The experiments have been conducted on Apple M4 Air chip with 10 CPU core, 8 GPU cores and 16 GB RAM. The experiments have been conducted using PyTorch framework. The hyperparameter used for the experiments are given in Table 1.

Table 1: ANN Hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	MNIST MLP	CIFAR-10 MLP
Input Dimension	784 (28x28)	3072 (3x32x32)
Hidden Layers	[256, 128]	[3072, 2048, 1024, 512]
Output Dimension	10 (Classes)	10 (Classes)
Activation Function	ReLU	ReLU
Layer Detachment	<i>All Hidden Layers</i>	<i>All Hidden Layers</i>
Readout Mechanism	Linear + Softmax	Linear + Softmax
Normalization	Frozen BatchNorm1d	Frozen BatchNorm1d
Epochs	10	30

4.2 Performance Baselines and Representation Quality

We compare the EGLP framework against widely used learning paradigms across supervised, unsupervised and non trainable settings across two datasets MNIST and CIFAR-10. The baselines include fully supervised backpropagation algorithm, a frozen random feature model where the hidden layers are initialized randomly, frozen and only the terminal readout layer being trained, unsupervised Hebbian learning and a hybrid learning mechanism with an unsupervised pretraining configuration followed by a linear probe evaluation. In the hybrid learning mechanism, the hidden layer are first pretrained using Hebbian learning and frozen while only the final classifier is optimized.

4.2.1 MNIST

The comparative results on the MNIST is summarized in Table 2. The backpropagation algorithm achieves the highest accuracy of 97.87% highlighting the advantage of using continuous gradient optimization for ANNs. In contrast unsupervised pretraining and linear probing approach achieves 87.31% followed by random frozen feature and EGLP that achieve accuracy of 86.93% and while the purely unsupervised Hebbian configuration reaches 83.52%.

Table 2: Performance Comparison on MNIST dataset

Paradigm	Test Accuracy	Learning Signals	Update Gating
Backpropagation	97.87%	Continuous	None
Random Features (Frozen)	86.93%	None	N/A
Pure Hebbian (Unsupervised)	86.90%	Continuous	None
EGLP	86.93%	Discrete (1,000)	Surprise Gated
Unsupervised Pretrain + Linear Probe	87.31%	None (Frozen)	N/A

The training dynamics of EGLP and backpropagation algorithm are compared in Figure 3. The backpropagation algorithm converges faster and achieves significantly higher accuracy compared to EGLP. However EGLP shows slower but stable convergence for both training and validation. Despite the sparse surprise triggered update mechanism, EGLP shows relatively small gap between training and validation curves indicating limited overfitting. However the early saturation of EGLP at lower accuracy level highlights the limitation in representational and optimization capacity of EGLP.

Figure 3: Training dynamics of ANN for backpropagation and EGLP on MNIST dataset

4.2.2 CIFAR-10

The comparative results of different learning paradigms are shown in Table 3. Due to increased dimensionality and complexity of images in CIFAR-10 dataset, the classification accuracy is lower than that of MNIST. The baseline algorithm achieves an accuracy of 53.75% outperforming all the baselines. The Random Features baseline collapses to 12.72%, which is slightly better than the random chance level (10%). EGLP achieves an accuracy of 39.60%, outperforming the random baseline and matching the performance of pure Hebbian learning (39.40%).

Table 3: Performance Comparison on CIFAR-10 dataset

Paradigm	Test Accuracy	Learning Signals	Update Gating
Backpropagation	53.75%	Continuous	None
Random Features (Frozen)	12.72%	None	N/A
Pure Hebbian (Unsupervised)	39.40%	Continuous	None
EGLP	39.60%	Discrete (1,000)	Surprise Gated
Unsupervised Pretrain + Linear Probe	37.79%	None (Frozen)	N/A

The training dynamics of ANN trained using backpropagation algorithm and EGLP is illustrated in Figure 4. Similar to the trends seen for MNIST dataset, the EGLP framework shows slower convergence compared to the backpropagation algorithm while maintaining relatively stable validation behavior. The performance between EGLP and backpropagation algorithm of approximately 14% highlights the limitation of current local learning rules in complex image classification tasks.

Figure 4: Training dynamics of ANN for backpropagation and EGLP on CIFAR-10 dataset

4.3 Scaling Laws and the Credit Assignment Vanishing Problem

To evaluate the scalability of EGLP framework in deeper architectures we systematically varied the depth of the architecture and the number of neurons per layer across the MNIST dataset. The objective of this experiment is to analyze how learning dynamics changes with depth of the ANN. Firstly we vary the depth of the architecture from 2 to 8 layers keeping a fixed hidden dimension of 256 neurons per layer. The performance across different architectural depths are shown in Table 4. The experiments show that the two layered ANN architecture achieves the highest accuracy, 90.49% however the accuracy consistently decreases with increase in depth of the ANN architecture. This indicated that the effectiveness of EGLP decreases with increasing depth. As the depth of the network increases the modulatory DFA signal, $m^{(l)}$ becomes less effective for coordinating lower layer representations and results in reduced classification performance.

Table 4: Depth Scaling Performance of EGLP on MNIST dataset

Hidden Layers	Architecture	Test Accuracy
2	[256, 256]	90.49%
4	[256, 256, 256, 256]	83.73%
6	[256, ..., 256]	75.20%
8	[256, ..., 256]	65.28%

4.4 Width Scaling and Capacity Expansion

We evaluated a fixed two layer EGLP architecture while varying the hidden layer width from 128 to 1024 neurons on the MNIST dataset. The experimental results are given in Table 5. The architecture with 1024 achieves 95.62% outperforming the other baselines. The results indicate that EGLP gets substantial benefit with increased representational capacity in shallow architectures.

Table 5: Width Scaling Performance of EGLP on MNIST dataset

Layer Width	Architecture	Test Accuracy
128	[128, 128]	85.18%
256	[256, 256]	90.49%
512	[512, 512]	93.61%
768	[768, 768]	94.72%
1024	[1024, 1024]	95.62%

4.5 Computational and Communication Efficiency

We compare the total FLOPs and the total number of hidden layer weight updates of EGLP with the backpropagation algorithm for 10 epochs over the MNIST dataset. The backpropagation algorithm requires approximately 5943.92 million FLOPs and nearly 4680 update events as it performs continuous updates in hidden layers throughout the training. In contrast, EGLP performs only 1000 update events through a surprise triggered gating mechanism and requires about 1981.31 million FLOPs.

Table 6: Efficiency Metrics

Model	Total FLOPs	Hidden Update Events
Backpropagation	5943.92 M	~4,680
EGLP	1981.31 M	1,000

4.6 Ablation Study: Structural Components

To evaluate the contribution of additional mechanism we analyzed the effect of incorporation of predictive coding and lateral inhibition [19] to EGLP. The experimental results of the ablation study is summarized in Table 7. The vanilla EGLP yields an accuracy of 86.93%, however incorporating predictive coding and lateral inhibition exhibit small decrease in performance.

Table 7: Ablation Analysis of EGLP Components

Configuration	Accuracy	Δ vs. Base
EGLP (Base)	86.93%	-
EGLP + Predictive + Inhibition	85.69%	-1.24%
EGLP + Predictive (No Inhibition)	85.64%	-1.29%

5 Discussions

The experimental results demonstrate that the EGLP framework can help to learn the meaningful representations under strictly local learning constraints. Additionally, EGLP uses significantly lesser number of hidden layer update and reduces computational cost. Across both MNIST and CIFAR-10 dataset, ELGP shows strong performance against Hebbian learning and consistently outperforms the random frozen features baseline. The addition of Hebbian plasticity, DFA and surprise based event gating helps EGLP to make the ANN effectively learn features without end to end gradient flow in the network. Moreover, the experimental results demonstrate the limitations of local learning frameworks in terms of representational and optimization capabilities. Although EGLP shows relatively stable convergence and small gap between training and validation curves, it saturates at lower accuracies compared to backpropagation algorithm. This is more evident in CIFAR-10 dataset where the performance gap is approximately 14%, highlighting the difficulty of applying local plasticity methods in complex computer vision tasks.

Furthermore, the depth scaling experiments reveal the key weakness of local plasticity learning mechanisms. The performance of EGLP framework decreases substantially with increase in depth of the network suggesting ineffective credit assignment in deep architectures. As the hidden layers of the ANN are detached from the gradient propagation, DFA based modulatory signals become less effective in guiding representations towards global learning objective specifically in lower layers. In contrast the width scaling experiments show that EGLP framework gains substantial benefit from larger representational capacity in shallow network. This suggest that in shallow architectures increasing

the width may compensate for the absence of global gradient propagation by allowing local plasticity rule to capture more expressive representations. Finally, the EGLP requires lesser number of FLOPs update events as compared to backpropagation algorithm. However the efficiency of EGLP comes at the cost of weaker optimization and lower representational capabilities.

6 Conclusion and Future Works

In this study we investigated EGLP, a biologically inspired local plasticity framework incorporating Hebbian learning, DFA and surprise triggered event gating. The experimental results highlight that EGLP can learn meaningful representation with significantly lesser hidden layer update events and computational cost. However, the study reveals the important limitation of existing local plasticity methods specifically in terms of optimization capability, feature representation, and scalability in deeper architectures. While EGLP shows strong results in shallow wide architectures, a substantial performance gap on CIFAR-10 dataset highlight the challenges of credit assignment under strictly local learning constraints.

A number of research directions can be explored as part of future works. Firstly improving the credit assignment and feature representation in deep architectures needs to be addressed. Additionally strategies such as adaptive modulatory feedback mechanisms [20], dynamic local objectives [21], neuromorphic architectures [22, 23], hybrid gradient and local learning strategies [24] may also be explored. Furthermore, extending EGLP to advanced architectures such as CNNs [25] and Transformers [26] can also provide deeper insights.

Source Code Availability

The source code is accessible in the following GitHub Repository:

<https://github.com/debg48/EGLP>

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